

The Impact of the Songket Industry on the Economy of Palembang City, South Sumatra, Indonesia

M. Yusuf ¹, Rita Martini ², Muhammad Riska Maulana Effendi³

^{1,3} Sriwijaya State Polytechnic, Department of Business Administration, Palembang, South Sumatra, Indonesia

² Sriwijaya State Polytechnic, Department of Accounting, Palembang, South Sumatra, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

One of the economic missions of the Indonesian Government is to promote the creative economy, micro, small and medium enterprises, and entrepreneurship to create jobs. The songket industry is one of the creative economic activities that supports Indonesia's economy, especially in Palembang City. The purpose of this study is to determine the impact of the songket industry on the economy of Palembang City. This type of research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. The study was conducted on the songket industry in Palembang City. The songket industries sampled in the study totaled 2 songket industries which are pioneers of the songket industry in Palembang City. The samples were divided based on the regional division of Palembang City, namely Seberang Ulu and Seberang Ilir. The analysis in the study used data obtained from interviews with business actors, the government, and the community. To support the research results, analysis was also carried out through direct observation and documentation study. The research results provide information that the songket industry plays a role in the formation and economic growth of Palembang City. The songket industry is a Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) that provides the largest product domestic regional bruto (PDRB) contribution to Palembang City from the MSMEs sector. The songket industry is able to increase PDRB, shown by a continuously increasing trend, increase employment, encourage increased innovation and technology, and become one of the mainstay tourism sectors. The growing industrial sector helps in economic diversification. The government should pay attention to the growth of the songket industry sector by strengthening capital enhancement, human resource development, and songket tourism promotion.

KEYWORDS: Songket industry, MSMEs, economic growth, PDRB, employment, tourism sector.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
11 May 2026

Available on:
<https://irijsh.com/>

1. INTRODUCTION

Palembang Songket is one of the cultural works from South Sumatra that was designated as Indonesian Cultural Heritage by the Ministry of Education and Culture in 2013, Number 201300009. Songket is often associated with the Srivijaya Empire as the origin of the songket tradition in Palembang, which was the center of the Srivijaya kingdom. Songket has also become popular in the Maritime Southeast Asia Region, especially in neighboring countries such as Brunei, Malaysia, and Singapore, to this day.

The songket weaving craft is not only a cultural heritage but also plays an important role in the economic progress of Palembang. The songket industry is a creative economic activity and falls under the category of micro, small, and medium enterprises (better known in Indonesia by the abbreviation MSMEs). Songket is one of the main focuses of the creative industry in Palembang that has contributed to the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) of Palembang City post-Covid-19 (Central Bureau Statistics or BPS, 2025). Studies on songket in South Sumatra generally discuss the philosophical value of songket motifs, songket-making techniques, profiles of songket weaving artisans, and promotion strategies for Palembang Songket (Viatra and Triyanto, 2014; Salim, 2016; Tahrir et al., 2017; Irmeilyana and Desiani, 2018; Berlian, 2018; Hasan and Liliana, 2020). However, the role of songket itself needs to be examined in terms of the economic impact of the songket industry.

According to a view in line with the World Bank, the creative economy plays a crucial role as a driver of sustainable economic growth and poverty alleviation (Acemoglu & James, 2008). This sector spurs innovation, creates new jobs, and increases the country's global competitiveness through the utilization of ideas, skills, and digital technology. The impact of the songket industry on the economy of Palembang City needs to be studied, especially in determining policies regarding the songket industry. Palembang

The Impact of the Songket Industry on the Economy of Palembang City, South Sumatra, Indonesia

City, located in South Sumatra Province, is part of the territory of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia that supports the government's economic vision and mission focused on "Together with an Advanced Indonesia, Towards a Golden Indonesia 2045". This economic policy direction is outlined in eight main missions called Asta Cita, which aim to achieve a just, prosperous, sovereign, and independent society.

Based on information from the Ministry of State Secretariat of the Republic of Indonesia (<https://www.setneg.go.id/>), the Economic missions outlined in Asta Cita are as follows:

1. Food, Energy, and Water Self-Sufficiency: Achieve national self-reliance by ensuring the independent availability of food, energy, and water.
2. Downstreaming and Industrialization: Continue downstreaming of natural resource-based and maritime industries to increase domestic value added.
3. High Economic Growth: Target economic growth of up to 8% by strengthening the people's economy.
4. Poverty Eradication: Accelerate poverty alleviation by strengthening development from villages and from the grassroots.
5. Job Creation & Entrepreneurship Enhancement: Promote the creative economy, MSMEs, and entrepreneurship to create quality jobs.
6. Human Resource Strengthening: Build excellent human resources through education, technology, and health.
7. Increased State Revenue: Establish a state revenue agency and increase the state revenue-to-GDP ratio to 23 percent.
8. Equitable Development: Continue infrastructure development and inclusive economic equity.

The songket fabric industry plays a significant role in the economy of Palembang City, especially in the creative industry sector. Songket fabric is characteristic of activities in Palembang City, such as traditional wedding gifts, circumcision ceremonies, clothing for formal events, gifts for state and regional guests, and other needs. As a cultural heritage with high prestige value, songket is also one of the leading tourist attractions of Palembang City. Tourists often seek songket as a premium souvenir. This shows that the songket industry presents a great opportunity for artisans. Songket enthusiasts today do not always come from certain circles, but all groups can become buyers. This means that production quantity can increase daily depending on consumer needs. The development of the songket industry in Palembang City must certainly pay attention to industrial activities that include the production of goods and services, create employment, and make a significant contribution to the gross regional domestic income of Palembang City. The development of the songket industry must also be accompanied by addressing the obstacles faced by industry players so that economic activities can be sustainable.

The purpose of this study is to determine the impact of the songket industry on the economy of Palembang City.

2. METHODOLOGY

This type of research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. This approach was chosen to deeply understand the impact of the songket industry as a creative economy on the economy of Palembang City. The study was conducted in Palembang City. According to data from the Palembang City Industry and Tourism Office (2023), the number of songket industries is 121 businesses. The sample in this study consisted of 2 songket industries which are pioneers of the songket industry in Palembang City and were divided based on the regional division of Palembang City, namely Seberang Ulu and Seberang Ilir. The focus of this study is the impact of the songket industry on the economy of Palembang City with the scope of study limited to Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP), employment, value-added enhancement, and tourism. The analysis in the study used data obtained from interviews, direct observation, and documentation study. The data collection techniques are:

1. Conducting in-depth interviews with business actors in the songket industry sector, local government, and the community,
2. Directly observing songket industry activities in the field,
3. Documentation study collecting secondary data from government reports, academic publications, and statistical data related to the songket industry.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The songket industry is believed to be a distinctive woven craft of the Palembang people. Looking at its history, this craft has existed since the time of the Srivijaya Kingdom. Therefore, it is not surprising that in Palembang, which was the center of the Srivijaya Kingdom, people were already familiar with the songket weaving craft earlier. Palembang is not only the center of the Srivijaya kingdom, but also the capital of South Sumatra. Thus, it is natural that it would advance earlier with various developments. From its history, it can be assumed that songket weaving in Palembang is the result of acculturation with other cultures that entered Palembang, such as Chinese and Indian.

In its development, knowledge about songket weaving began to spread. Along with its development, more and more people became interested in pursuing the songket industry. At the next stage, the community has begun to think progressively, meaning that songket weaving is not only regarded as knowledge of local crafts, but can also be relied upon as a source of livelihood for the community.

Although its production is still very simple, songket has always experienced developments in motifs or patterns, such as plant or floral motifs known as songket bunga.

Songket bunga consists of two types, namely bunga emas and bunga pacik. These two types of floral patterns are distinguished by the type of thread used. Songket bunga emas is widely used by people of Chinese descent, while songket bunga pacik uses white cotton thread and is widely used by people of Arab descent (Efriyanto, 2022). Floral motifs then became more diverse, known as songket lepus biasa, songket sadem, songket bungo cino, and others. One artisan also explained that the songket weaving motifs made are very varied, depending on needs and contemporary styles. These diverse motifs are certainly supported by the development of thread as the basic material. In the past, people only used limar thread to make songket because that was all that was available. However, now there are many types of thread that can be used, one example being natural silk thread. It can be seen that the work of songket weaving regarding changes in motifs is closely linked to the level of creativity of the community itself. Changes in these various songket motifs have then influenced the development of songket prices themselves. In the past, songket prices were considered relatively low, but the development of better songket patterns has ultimately made songket prices higher (Sahidah, 2022). Songket fabric is one of the unique and remarkable works. Besides reflecting the wisdom, creativity, and progress of the community, it also contains human, religious, and local cultural wisdom values which then direct it to become a symbol embodied in the form of clothing that represents nobility for the wearer (Rusmin, 2010). Therefore, it is highly inappropriate if such a culture were to be forgotten. Songket is an asset whose preservation deserves to be maintained through various efforts.

Based on observation, there are several efforts that have been made to continue the sustainability of the songket industry, both by the government and by songket industry players, namely: Introducing and teaching the younger generation through arts and culture education in schools as well as songket weaving training programs. Promotion by routinely holding Songket Festivals, seminars or workshops, and other major events. Maintaining the authenticity of materials by consistently preserving quality. The government also assists in terms of facilitating the procurement of raw materials. From the research results obtained regarding the development and efforts that have been made, it shows that the songket industry is a continuous and sustainable activity. This is certainly expected to have an impact on the economy of Palembang City.

Based on the research results, it is known that the songket industry as a creative economy has major impacts on the economy of Palembang City, including GRDP Trend 2022-2025:

1. The overall GRDP of Palembang City has continued to increase, reaching IDR 208.19 trillion in 2024. Although specific data for the songket industry (as a subsector) is not detailed in the general publication summary of BPS (2025), the manufacturing industry (where songket is categorized) consistently remains a main contributor in the report. The Songket Industry continues to experience an increasing trend where in 2022 it was 5 percent, in 2023 it was 5.5 percent, in 2024 it was 5.7 percent, and in 2025 it was 6.1 percent. It is expected that in 2026 it will reach 6.5 to 7 percent.
2. Job creation and unemployment reduction: This industry absorbs labor in various fields such as songket design, advertising, and technology, which directly reduces the unemployment rate. The exact number of labor absorption in the Songket industry is unknown, but based on data from the Palembang City Cooperatives and MSMEs Office (2025), the number of MSMEs (including songket centers) has reached more than 80,000 units. This indicates that more and more business actors are engaged in MSMEs in the songket industry, which of course also increases labor absorption. The growth of the songket industry in Palembang City indicates that this sector plays a role in supporting post-Covid-19 pandemic recovery and growth.
3. The songket industry continues to be strengthened through economic empowerment strategies for artisans to maintain industry sustainability and provide jobs, especially with the potential for artisan regeneration (Generation Z) in the songket weaving industry. This industry absorbs both female and male labor. The characteristics of the workforce in this industry still predominantly involve local labor. The division of gender roles greatly influences the socio-economic landscape in Palembang's songket centers.
4. Increased value added of products/services: Creativity and innovation transform conventional products into high-selling value goods, increase profits, and strengthen brand competitiveness. Encouraging innovation and technology in the creative industry spurs the development of new technologies and accelerates digital adoption. Increased tourism: Through the promotion of local culture and creative works that attract tourists, which provides direct economic impact. In addition, it can build the country's image through cultural and traditional diversity. Preservation of local culture and community empowerment are also positive outcomes of the development of this sector.

In this study, challenges were found in the songket industry, such as technological developments that require large capital, human resource development in facing technological changes, and minimal promotion in the tourism sector related to the songket industry, which is a tradition of Palembang City. Therefore, effective strategies from the government and stakeholders are needed to overcome these challenges. Flexibility and innovation in the creative economy enable business actors to adapt quickly to market changes. With advances in digital technology, small business actors can expand their market access globally, reducing geographical limitations. The creative economy also creates inclusive participation spaces for various community groups, including women and persons with disabilities.

Protection of intellectual property rights is important to encourage innovation and protect creative works. Collaboration between the government, private sector, academics, and creative communities is essential to build an ecosystem that supports the growth of this sector. With the right strategies, the creative economy can become a main pillar in national development, not only driving economic growth but also improving the quality of life and overall welfare of society.

However, challenges such as limited capital, low digital literacy, and protection of intellectual property rights remain obstacles that need to be addressed. Therefore, collaboration between the government, private sector, and creative communities is crucial to create an ecosystem that supports the growth of the creative economy.

4. CONCLUSION

The songket industry plays a role in the formation and growth of the economy of Palembang City. The benefits of the industry to the economy of Palembang City are shown by the increase in GRDP, job creation along with the growth of the songket industry, improved labor skills, competition that drives increased innovation and technology, and being one of the mainstay tourism sectors. A growing industrial sector helps in economic diversification. Countries with strong industrial sectors can be more resilient to global market fluctuations.

REFERENCES

- 1) Acemoglu, Daron & James Robinson. (2008). The Role Of Institutions Growth And Development. Working Paper No. 10. The World Bank On Behalf of the Commission on Growth and Development. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/4d672573-6bbe-5213-a708-0b7604f9552c/>
- 2) Berlian, Z. (2018). Strategi Promosi Songket Palembang (Studi Kasus Kerajinan Songket Cek Ipah). *An Nisa'a*, 13(1). *Danadyaksa Historica 2 (2) (2022)*: 131–140
- 3) BPS. (2025). *Pertumbuhan Ekonomi Kota Palembang*. <https://palembangkota.bps.go.id/id/pressrelease/2026/03/05/1369/pertumbuhan-ekonomi-tw-iv-tahun-2025-kota-palembang.html>
- 4) Dinas Industri dan Pariwisata. (2023). *Pemetaan Potensi Pengembangan UMKM dan Indusrti Berbasis Keluarga*. https://asik.palembang.go.id/uploads/LAPORAN_AKHIR_UMKM_1e4a4905f2.pdf
- 5) Efrianto. (2021). Songket Palembang, Seminar sehari. *Workshop songket Palembang*. Museum Negeri Sumatera Selatan, Rabu 01 Desember 2021.
- 6) Hasan, M. A., & Liliana, D. Y. (2020). Pengenalan Motif Songket Palembang Menggunakan Deteksi Tepi Canny, PCA dan KNN. *Jurnal Multinetics*, vol. 6,1-7.
- 7) Irmeilyana, I., & Desiani, A. (2018). Analisis perbandingan profil pengrajin di tiga sentra kerajinan tenun songket Palembang. *Jurnal Infomedia: Teknik Informatika, Multimedia & Jaringan*, 3(2), 58-63.
- 8) Kementerian Sekretariat Negara Republik Indonesia. (2025). *ASTA CITA*. <https://www.setneg.go.id/>
- 9) Salim, N. S. (2016). Kain Songket Palembang dengan Penerapan Teknik Batik sebagai Produk Fesyen. *Journal of Visual Art and Design*, 7(2), 92.
- 10) Tahrir, R., Rohidi, T. R., & Iswidayati, S. (2017). Makna Simbolis dan Fungsi Tenun Songket Bermotif Naga pada Masyarakat Melayu di Palembang Sumatera Selatan. *Catharsis*, 6(1), 9-18.
- 11) Viatra, A. W., & Triyanto, S. (2014). Seni Kerajinan Songket Kampoeng Tenundi Indralaya, Palembang. *Ekspresi Seni: Jurnal Ilmu Pengetahuan Dan Karya Seni*, 16(2), 168-183.